

PASS FREQUENCY AS A MEANS FOR INCREASED LATP PRODUCTIVITY

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ABSTRACT

Automated manufacturing of thermoplastic composites has gained increasing interest due to its potential for low-cost, high-rate production of composite structures. The matrix-dominated mechanical properties of a laminate manufactured by laser-assisted automated tape placement of thermoplastic composites are highly influenced by the selected processing parameters. Within this work, experimental analysis was conducted to investigate the effect of processing parameters and pass frequency on the laminate microstructure and short beam strength. In conjunction with mechanical characterisation, the process uses a thermo-mechanical model to simulate the thermal history of the manufacturing process. Two cylindrical mandrels with different diameters were used to vary the pass frequency whilst keeping the remaining process parameters constant. Findings show that increasing the pass frequency gradually increases the substrate temperature, reduces the specimen void content, and increases the short beam strength.

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to the long shelf life, high fracture toughness, and perceived recyclability, thermoplastic composites have gained interest in the aerospace industry. With composite materials making up more than 50% of structural weight of modern commercial aircraft, there is a growing need to manufacture thermoplastic composites more efficiently than by autoclave processing [1, 2]. As such, out-of-autoclave manufacturing, such as laser-assisted automated tape placement (LATP), may result in the production of low-cost thermoplastic composites with the potential for high-rate production. Additional benefits of in-situ consolidation of thermoplastic tape by LATP include lower energy consumption compared to autoclaving and reduced material waste [3]. However, as both the nip-point temperature and time under compaction are functions of time, manufacturing at high placement rates often results in a laminate with high porosity and lower levels of interlaminar bonding [4]. Therefore, processes need to be developed to ensure high levels of interlaminar bonding without compromising the production rate of composite laminates.

Several studies have compared the effect of placement rate on the short beam strength (SBS) of LATP laminates [5, 6]. Kirchhoff *et al.* [6] found that increasing the placement rate by 6 m/min at a constant processing temperature reduced the SBS of the laminate by 27% due to an increase in the void content. However, processing temperature can only be increased up to a certain level, noting that exceeding this critical temperature results in matrix degradation and reductions in SBS [7, 8].

Post-processing of LATP laminates in an autoclave has been demonstrated to reduce void content and increase SBS, resulting in laminates with properties comparable to those of autoclaved laminates [9]. However, the requirement for post-processing of LATP manufactured laminates may negate some of the cost and environmental benefits associated with in-situ consolidation. Alternative methods to post-processing, such as repress treatment or the use of a heated tool, have been studied as a means for improving laminate quality. However, repress treatment extends the required manufacturing time,

reducing the overall production rate [10], while the use of a heated tool may not prove beneficial for thick laminates [1] and involves greater energy costs. Therefore, alternative modifications to the manufacturing process may be necessary to increase laminate production without compromising quality.

Within this work, the time-temperature relationship during LATP manufacturing is studied, as well as the influence of substrate temperature on laminate microstructure and subsequent SBS. Specifically, while previous studies [11-13] have indicated that maintaining the substrate temperature of a laminate during manufacturing reduces the void content and increases the SBS, there is limited research on methods for maintaining substrate temperature without the use of an additional heat source.

3 MATERIAL AND METHODOLOGY

3.1 Material and Manufacturing Methods

Manufacturing trials were conducted using an AFPT GmbH produced laser-assisted automated tape placement system located within the University of Limerick. The LATP system consisted of a 3kW laser heat source attached to a Kuka robotic arm (Kuka, KR 240 L210-2). A thermal camera monitors the temperature of the incoming tape, substrate, and nip point, adjusting the laser power to maintain the programmed target temperature in a closed-loop system.

Unidirectional, 12 mm wide, carbon fibre/PEEK tape was used to manufacture a total of 14 wound specimens, with a layup of $[0^\circ]_{30}$, using the processing parameters defined in Table 1. Specimens were manufactured with a constant pneumatic piston pressure of 2.5 Bar. Two cylindrical mandrels with two diameters were used: a large mandrel (diameter 250 mm) and a small mandrel (diameter 70 mm), to study the influence of pass frequency on the laminate microstructure and mechanical properties. Within the scope of this work, specimens are identified by the mandrel size (L or S, where Group L and S represent the specimens manufactured by large and small mandrels, respectively), the placement rate, and the processing temperature, as shown in Table 1. The pass frequency is defined as the inverse of the time required for one complete rotation of the mandrel, with different mandrel diameters resulting in different pass frequencies at the same placement rate, as shown in Table 2. Applying this naming convention, a specimen produced on the larger diameter mandrel at a placement rate of 9 m/min with a nominal nip point temperature of 450 °C is designated L-9-450.

Water jet cutting was used to extract specimens from the hoop laminate, ensuring a length of 40 mm for all specimens, as depicted in Fig. 1(a).

Parameters	Placement Rate (m/min)		
Temperature (°C)	3	9	15
400	3-400	9-400	15-400
450	3-450	9-450	15-450
500	3-500	9-500	15-500

Table 1: Processing parameters used during manufacturing. ID protocol consists of S or L (small or large, respectively) followed by process parameters.

Placement Rate (m/min)	Group S (Hz)	Group L (Hz)
3	0.228	0.058
9	0.680	0.173
15	1.136	0.287

Table 2: Pass frequency for two mandrel diameters and three placement rates used during manufacturing.

3.3 Characterisation and Analysis

Specimen void content was analysed using digital microscopy. The interlaminar bond line thickness was measured via point-to-point measurements at three locations within the overall specimen cross-section. Using the mandrel surface as a datum (0%) and the outer surface as the maximum value (100%), the bond line measurements were taken at 25%, 50%, and 75% of the specimen thickness.

As the degree of crystallinity can influence matrix-dominated mechanical properties, such as the short beam strength, digital scanning calorimetry (DSC) was conducted using a Netzsch 214 Polyma. The degree of crystallinity was tested for both the lower and upper surfaces of the specimen. Samples of 5-10 mg were taken from the specimens. A heating rate of 10 °C/min was used up to a maximum temperature of 400 °C. The degree of crystallinity is calculated from:

$$X_c = \frac{\Delta H_m - \Delta H_c}{\Delta H_{100} \times w_m} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where ΔH_m is the melt enthalpy (J/g), ΔH_c is the cold crystallisation enthalpy (J/g), w_m is the mass fraction of the matrix (0.34), and ΔH_{100} is the full crystallisation enthalpy of PEEK (130 J/g) [14].

Mechanical testing of the short beam strength (SBS) was conducted in accordance with ASTM D2344 [15] for a curved specimen as depicted in Fig. 1(b). Specimens were loaded with a constant displacement rate of 1 mm/min using a Tinius Olsen H25K-S with a 5 kN load cell. The maximum load was recorded for each specimen, with SBS calculated using:

$$SBS = 0.75 \frac{P}{t \times w} \quad (2)$$

where P is the maximum load (N), t is the sample thickness (mm), and w is the sample width (mm).

A 2D thermo-mechanical model was developed to simulate the incoming tape and substrate on both mandrel diameters, providing the through-thickness temperature distribution during manufacturing. This model aids the discussion and understanding of the mechanisms at play during manufacturing. The model is based on, and validated by, previous work completed by Ma *et al.* [16]. Due to computational power limitations, only the initial four plies placed are modelled in this work. Further details of the computational model can be found in Tobin *et al.* [17].

Figure 1: (a) SBS specimen geometry and (b) SBS loading set-up

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Computational Temperature Evolution

Thermo-mechanical modelling of the manufacturing process helps develop an understanding of the observed failure mechanisms. An initial comparison of the small and large mandrel models indicates that the simulated peak temperature on the incoming tape shows good agreement with the experimental processing temperature, indicating the acceptable accuracy of the model predictions.

When comparing the temperature evolution as shown in Fig. 2(a) and Fig. 3(a), it is apparent that higher substrate temperatures are reached in the small rather than the large mandrel. When placing ply two at a placement rate of 3 m/min and a processing temperature of 400 °C, ply 1 of S-3-400 reached a

maximum temperature of 400 °C, compared to 330 °C for L-3-400. However, it is worth noting that the substrate of L-3-400 remains below the melt temperature of PEEK during manufacturing, inhibiting interlaminar bonding. As the target temperature increases, computational thermal analysis indicates that the substrate reaches higher temperatures (Fig. 2(b) and Fig. 3(b)), with the large mandrel specimens being more sensitive to an increase in process temperature. The temperature sensitivity observed in the large mandrel specimens likely results from the difference in laser reflection patterns for the two mandrel diameters, which can be considered a limitation associated with the use of different mandrel diameters [17]. Analysing the temperature of the substrate for each layer suggests that the substrate temperature gradually increases with each rotation of the small mandrel, but not with the large mandrel. This observation becomes more apparent when comparing S-9-500 (Fig. 2(c)) and L-9-500 (Fig. 3(c)). For S-9-500, the first ply reaches a minimum temperature of 210 °C after the third layer is placed, however, L-9-500 cools to room temperature between each laser pass. When comparing L-9-500 to L-3-500, it is noted that the substrate temperature is lower for L-9-500 due to reduced time during the heating phase. While there is no thermo-mechanical model for placement rates of 15 m/min, it can be surmised that the observed trends when increasing the placement rate from 3 m/min to 9 m/min remain for higher placement rates. When considering the thermal history shown in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3, the influence of processing parameters can be inferred: increasing the processing temperature increases the substrate temperature, and increasing the placement rate can reduce the maximum temperature reached in the substrate while also reducing the cooling time. Additionally, comparing the thermal history displayed in both Figs. 2 and 3, it is noted that increasing the laser pass frequency can introduce gradual heating in the substrate, which can increase the degree of interlaminar bonding when manufacturing at high placement rates.

Figure 2: Thermal history of (a) S-3-400, (b) S-3-500 and (c) S-9-500. Different colours correspond to the ply placed (first ply to fourth ply).

Figure 3: Thermal history of (a) L-3-400, (b) L-3-500 and (c) L-9-500. Each colour corresponds to the thermal history of the ply placed (first ply to fourth ply).

4.2 Microstructure Variation

Initial, qualitative comparison between laminate microstructures indicates that mandrel diameter and processing parameters affect the void content, location, and interlaminar bond line thickness. Specimen S-9-450 had the lowest overall void content (0.2%), whereas the highest void content was for L-3-400 (2.25%). When comparing the void content within both specimen groups at equivalent processing parameters, the void content in the small mandrel specimens was found to be lower than that in the large mandrel specimens (Fig. 4(a)). This difference was most apparent when manufacturing at 500 °C and 15 m/min, where the void content difference was 1.75% (Fig. 4(a)).

When considering the influence of processing parameters on void content, at low placement rates (3 m/min), increasing the processing temperature reduced the overall void content of the laminate. When considering the thermal history of the specimens, increasing the processing temperature resulted in a higher substrate temperature, which facilitates higher levels of interlaminar bonding due to increased matrix flow across the interlaminar bond line. By increasing the placement rate at a constant processing temperature, the void content increases, with the most prominent increase in void content observed when manufacturing on the large mandrel at 15 m/min. As previously mentioned, the level of interlaminar bonding is a function of the processing time, with an increase in placement rate reducing the laminate time under temperature or consolidation force. Fig. 3(c) shows that an increase in placement rate for the large mandrel reduces the maximum temperature reached by the substrate, which can serve to explain the void content observed in L-15-500. However, due to the gradual substrate heating with high pass frequency (Fig. 2(c)), S-15-500 has a lower void content than L-15-500 despite the maximum substrate temperature being relatively low.

In addition to void content variation, the predominant type of void observed, interlaminar or intralaminar, varied with processing parameters and mandrel diameter. Within the small mandrel specimens, intralaminar voids were the dominant void type for all processing parameters. However, specimens manufactured on the large mandrel exhibited both types of voids. At low placement rates (3 m/min), intralaminar voids were more prominent within specimens manufactured on the large mandrel, with few interlaminar voids observed. At higher placement rates, interlaminar voids became prominent. The void type occurs as a function of the tape temperature. According to thermal simulations, the substrate of L-9-500 remains below the melt temperature of PEEK, which can inhibit intimate contact formation, causing interlaminar voids to occur. While simulations were not conducted for a 15 m/min placement rate due to the associated computational costs, it can be assumed that this temperature difference would be exacerbated. Intralaminar voids can occur due to tape deconsolidation, as heating the tape can introduce void growth and migration, and rapid cooling reduces matrix flow [18]. Increasing the tape temperature to ensure the matrix is above the melt temperature allows intralaminar voids to be fully compacted during consolidation [19]. Additionally, increasing the pass frequency above 1 Hz at a constant placement rate can maintain a temperature above the glass transition temperature, which facilitates void compaction.

While there was little evidence of interlaminar voids within the small mandrel specimens, there were observed differences in the interlaminar bond line between the two mandrel size groups. An interlaminar resin-rich bond line is readily observed in all specimens; it was noted that increasing the processing temperature at a constant placement rate reduces the bond line thickness. For example, L-3-400, L-3-450, and L-3-500 had a resin-rich bond line thickness of 12.44, 8.74, and 7.92 μm , respectively. However, the bond line thicknesses for the small mandrel specimens are significantly lower than those for the equivalent large mandrel specimens, with S-3-400, S-3-450, and S-3-500 having bond line thicknesses of 9.73, 7.93, and 6.60 μm , respectively. Increasing the placement rate resulted in an increase in the bond line thickness at a constant processing temperature for both mandrel diameters. Despite an increase in the resin-rich bond line thickness with increasing placement rate, the observed trend of small mandrel specimens having a thinner resin-rich region was consistent. Additional observed differences between the mandrel size groups reflect the ply structure, with small mandrel specimens displaying significant out-of-plane ply waviness at high placement rates.

Figure 4: (a) Void content for processing parameters and (b) Void content variation with pass frequency

The degree of crystallinity can influence the mechanical properties of the matrix and, therefore, affect the SBS. When comparing the degree of crystallinity between the upper and lower surfaces, it is observed that the lower surface has a lower degree of crystallinity than the upper surface. Additionally, the upper surface's microstructure was found to be insensitive to changes in process parameters. When considering the degree of crystallinity at the lower surface, it is noted that at 3 m/min, increasing the processing temperature results in a five percent increase in the degree of crystallinity for both mandrel types. However, the average degree of crystallinity ranges between 20% and 25% (Fig. 5(a)), with the mandrel size and pass frequency having little effect on the average degree of crystallinity (Fig. 5(b)). When comparing the two mandrel sizes with equivalent processing parameters, it is observed that there was a 2-5% difference in degree of crystallinity, falling within the error margin of this analysis, despite the difference in pass frequency.

Figure 5: (a) Average crystallinity for specimens and (b) Crystallinity variation with pass frequency

4.3 SBS and Failure

The influence of processing parameters on SBS values is displayed in Fig. 6(a), with the effect of pass frequency shown in Fig. 6(b). A maximum SBS of 58 MPa is achieved with S-9-450. However, this value is still significantly lower than the expected SBS from an autoclave specimen (112 MPa [1]). From Fig. 6(a), it is noted that the specimens manufactured on the small mandrel have a higher SBS than the equivalent large mandrel specimens. Initial assumptions for this apparent difference are based on geometric differences; however, according to finite element simulations (Details on simulation available in Tobin *et al.* [17]), geometrical differences in specimens in this study have a negligible effect

on the SBS value. Additionally, the difference between SBS values for small and large mandrels is not consistent across the process parameters. This observation, combined with the knowledge that the degree of crystallinity can be considered equivalent for the two mandrel types, indicates that the pass frequency affects the SBS.

Comparing the influence of processing parameters on the SBS of both mandrel diameters indicates that the large mandrel specimens are more sensitive to variations in temperature and placement rate (Fig. 6(a)). Comparing L-3-500 to L-9-500, the increase in placement rate results in a reduction in substrate temperature in the large mandrel specimen, correlating with a 6% decrease in SBS. With an increased placement rate, there was a reduction in exposure time to laser flux, thereby reducing the maximum temperatures reached in the substrate. At a placement rate of 9 m/min and temperature of 500 °C, the first ply of L-9-500 reached a temperature of roughly 350 °C, with no subsequent ply reaching the melt temperature. Although above the matrix melt temperature (343 °C), as shown in Fig. 3(c), a rapid drop in temperature occurs due to the cooling effect of the consolidation roller. It can be assumed that a similar thermal history trend exists when further increasing the placement rate to 15 m/min. As a result, void growth, void migration, and fibre decompaction can occur during the heating phase, but the rapid temperature drop during consolidation prevents matrix flow [18]. The high void content in the large mandrel specimens, as a result of low processing temperature, can serve to explain the further reduction in SBS at 15 m/min, as there is a documented correlation between void content and SBS.

The range of SBS observed for large mandrel specimens is 23-47 MPa, compared to a variation of 48-58 MPa for the small mandrel specimens. The consistency of SBS results for the small mandrel specimens indicates that higher pass frequency can be beneficial for SBS. As there is a correlation between void content and SBS [20], specimens with low overall void content have higher SBS values. As observed with void content measurements, the large mandrel specimens were more sensitive to the temperature increase than the smaller mandrel specimens due to the difference in substrate temperatures. It was determined that increasing the processing temperature resulted in a reduction in void content and interlaminar bond line thickness for both mandrel diameters when processing at a speed of 3 m/min. The simulated thermal history for both mandrels indicates that increasing the processing temperature results in an increase in the substrate temperature. The increase in substrate temperature reduces matrix viscosity, which facilitates void compaction during manufacturing. This reduction in void content and matrix bond line width increases the SBS for the specimen, as voids act as stress concentrations and therefore serve as crack initiators.

Figure 6: (a) Average SBS for processing parameters and (b) SBS variation with pass frequency

To understand the failure mechanism of SBS specimens, microscopical analysis was conducted to compare the failure locations and fracture surfaces. Fig. 7(a-b) displays the failure crack for the specimen with the lowest (L-3-400) and the highest SBS values (S-9-450). From Fig. 7(a), it is noted that failure occurs along the interlaminar bond line, with little to no crack deflection observed. This failure likely

occurs due to relatively poor interlaminar bonding as a result of a substrate temperature that was too low, as indicated in Fig. 3(a). When analysing the fracture surfaces of L-3-400, which had clear interlaminar failure, no sign of matrix deformation is observed (Fig. 7(c)), further indicating poor interlaminar bonding. Contrary to the interlaminar failure observed for L-3-400, failure S-9-450 occurred within the ply with significant crack deflection (Fig. 7 (b)). When analysing the failure surface of S-9-450 in Fig. 7(d), there are signs of matrix deformation correlating with the higher SBS value. Additionally, S-9-450 has significant matrix remaining on the fibre surfaces, indicating high levels of fibre-matrix adhesion, probably due to increased processing temperature, which improves the fibre-matrix bonding.

Figure 7: Fractured mid-plane of (a) L-3-400 and (b) S-9-450, and fracture surface of (c) L-3-400 and (d) S-9-450

4.4 The effect of pass frequency on SBS

While the effect of processing parameters on the SBS has been documented within Section 4.3, the influence of pass frequency on the microstructure and subsequent SBS variations has yet to be discussed. While there may be a difference in residual stress formation within the specimens due to the different mandrel diameters, Ma *et al.* [16] showed that variations in residual stress do not correlate with changes in the SBS. Changes, therefore, occur as a result of differences in the specimen's microstructure. As the consolidation force was held constant during manufacturing, the difference in microstructure between the two mandrel geometries can be explained by comparing their thermal histories.

In order to ensure intralaminar void compaction, the matrix should be held above the melt temperature [19]. However, once the matrix is above the glass transition temperature, it is possible to compress interlaminar and intralaminar voids [21]. From Fig. 2(c) and Fig. 3(c), it is noted that the substrate temperature of S-9-500 gradually increases, whereas for L-9-500 it does not. The increases in substrate temperature occur due to an increase in pass frequency from 0.173 Hz to 0.680 Hz. At elevated pass frequencies, the LATP head completes a full rotation of the mandrel before the previous ply fully cools, with the next ply being placed onto a warm substrate. The increase in substrate temperature at high pass frequencies is similar to the higher substrate temperature introduced while manufacturing on a heated tool, which has been shown to reduce void content and increase SBS [22]. Although the thermal history of manufacturing at 15 m/min was not simulated, the trends observed for S-9-500 and L-9-500 are likely to occur at a higher placement rate. Specifically, the substrate temperature of the specimens manufactured on the small mandrel at 15 m/min will not have fully cooled at a pass frequency of 1.136 Hz. This effect is due to the higher pass frequency, which results in lower void content in S-15-450 and S-15-500 compared to both L-15-450 and L-15-500. Despite the substrate temperature being lower at

high placement rates (Fig. 2 and Fig. 3), the substrate remains above the glass transition temperature for longer, which facilitates void compaction and interlaminar bonding.

The thermal history variation between the two mandrels highlights that increasing the pass frequency can aid in maintaining the substrate temperature, thereby reducing void content, and subsequently increasing the SBS. However, from Fig. 5(b) and Fig. 6(b), it is noted that the relationship between pass frequency and SBS is non-monotonic, with a maximum SBS being achieved (S-9-450) and subsequently decreasing. However, it is also worth noting that the maximum SBS value also varies with mandrel geometry, as the laser flux varies with diameter. Using the relationship between void content and pass frequency as a metric for optimisation, with the lowest void content being considered optimum, it was noted that this optimum was achieved at 9 m/min and 450 °C (0.680 Hz), and with the void content increasing with increases in pass frequency. However, when manufacturing large structures, this level of pass frequency is likely unattainable when manufacturing with a single LAMP head. Therefore, future developments of the LAMP systems, such that they are similar to the thermoplastic pipe manufacturing industry, where multiple heads work in unison, may facilitate the required high pass frequency [23]. Based on the thermal histories displayed in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3, the maximum substrate temperature is highly dependent on the placement rate. In order to further increase the pass frequency, it is necessary to increase the processing temperature further. However, when comparing the maximum temperatures achieved when processing at a pass frequency of 0.173 Hz and 0.680 Hz, it is noted that with the same nip-point temperature, the higher pass frequency results in a substrate temperature approximately 100 °C higher. This temperature difference indicates that although there is a requirement for increasing the target nip-point temperature with higher placement rates, increasing the pass frequency results in a lower temperature being needed, reducing the potential for matrix degradation.

6 CONCLUSIONS

LAMP manufacturing was used to produce specimens on various diameter mandrels, allowing for the study of the effect of pass frequency on the specimen microstructure and subsequent variations in SBS. A thermo-mechanical finite element model was utilised to determine the thermal history of the laminates, providing a deeper understanding of the influence of processing on microstructural changes. Characterisation tests were conducted to analyse the influence of the microstructural changes due to pass frequency on the interlaminar bond strength through SBS testing.

Results show that increasing the placement rate increases the overall laminate void content due to insufficient matrix temperatures being reached. While the temperature is above the matrix glass transition temperature, at high placement rates (15 m/min), the substrate does not reach the melt temperature. This scenario facilitates tape deconsolidation while also inhibiting matrix flow, thereby increasing the void content. Due to an increase in void content, the maximum SBS obtained is 32 MPa (0.287 Hz). However, increasing the pass frequency to 1.136 Hz (57 MPa) at the same placement rate and temperature causes the substrate to gradually heat, increasing the window of time for consolidation to occur. Due to this gradual substrate heating, the void content reduced and SBS increased for equivalent process parameters, but at a higher pass frequency.

However, there are limitations associated with this study. While the use of two mandrel diameters introduced methods for varying the pass frequency, it became apparent that the laser flux was different for the two mandrel diameters. As a result, the maximum temperatures reached during ply placement differed for the same processing parameters. However, despite the temperature differences observed during initial placement, the thermal history trends with increasing pass frequency are expected to be representative. From the results and discussion presented in this work, it is apparent that a pass frequency of 0.680 Hz at 450 °C provided the highest SBS. However, for large-diameter structures, this pass frequency is likely unattainable with a single LAMP head. Therefore, this study aims to highlight potential future developments in LAMP manufacturing optimisation, aiming to achieve high-rate manufacturing without compromising interlaminar bond strength.

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